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Current advances in the synthesis and biological potencies of tri- and tetra-substituted 1H-imidazoles

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Abstract

In this report, we review the current chemistry progress and in particular the synthesis approaches of tri- and tetra-substituted imidazoles.

Keywords

Nonhuman, priority journal, Review, Imidazoles chemistry, procedures, synthesis, Chemistry Techniques